

COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE NATIONAL HEALTH INSURANCE PROGRAM (BPJS) HEALTH POLICY IN GARUT REGENCY

¹AAM PATHULOH, ²*LIA MULIAWATY, and ³UMMU SALAMAH

^{1,2,3} Universitas Pasundan, Bandung, Indonesia. *Email: lia.muliawaty@unpas.ac.id

Abstract

This study aims to describe and analyze collaborative governance steps in implementing policies for the National Health Insurance program through the Health Social Security Administration (BPJS) in Garut Regency. The method used in this study is a descriptive qualitative method and through data collection techniques carried out by observation, interviews with several sources, and documentation studies, and the results of this study indicate that the implementation of the JKN Program policy at BPJS Health in Garut Regency has been ongoing. Quite good, although it cannot be separated from several shortcomings, on the other hand aspects of the successful implementation of the policy are running properly in accordance with the applicable laws and regulations. However, in some aspects it shows an increase, such as the number of participants and the commitment of participants to pay membership dues, but in other aspects it has not been optimally implemented, including the readiness of all health resources including the availability of health human resources, health facilities, medical devices, and inadequate health budgets. Both in terms of quality and quantity. Then the steps for implementing this program policy are carried out through communication, coordination and collaboration between BPJS Health as the leading sector and related government institutions, private parties, stakeholders and also the community or program participants. Another step is through the provision of adequate health resources in quality and quantity, as well as a leadership disposition to influence staff and subordinate institutions to support each other's success in the program. The final step is to simplify the bureaucratic structure of the administration of services for participants or prospective program participants in order to obtain health services effectively and efficiently.

Keywords: Collaborative governance, JKN Program Implementation, BPJS Health

A. INTRODUCTION

Health is the human right of every person; this right has been documented for a long time in several international documents/agreements regarding the guarantee of a person's right to health. Articles 28 and 34 of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia state that health is a basic right of every citizen in the context of improving people's welfare. RI Law No.23/1992 in conjunction with RI Law No.36/2009 concerning Health also stipulates that everyone has the same rights in obtaining access to resources in the health sector and obtaining safe, quality, and affordable health services (Ansell & Gash, 2003). 2007).

The above law emphasizes the role and responsibility of the state to fulfill the basic needs of every citizen, namely to provide and ensure that citizens receive proper health services. This must be supported and involve various parties through effective governance, both from the government, private and community sectors. The involvement of various parties through mapping and identification of health problems shows the potential to develop and advance health care programs through collaboration of available resources. The collaboration begins with a development plan that is discussed by the Central Government, Provincial

Government, Regency/City Government, and related agencies through deliberation to streamline the implementation of the health service policy program, namely Collaborative Governance. However, with the many dynamics that occur, the health insurance sector is centralized back to the center through the formation of the Social Security Administration Agency (BPJS).

The BPJS institution was formed to administer social security programs in Indonesia. This refers to the Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 40 of 2004 concerning the National Social Security System (SJSN) and the Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 24 of 2011 concerning BPJS. The government appointed PT Askes (Persero) as the provider of social security in the health sector. This company later changed to BPJS Health. One of its products is the National Health Insurance Program-Healthy Indonesia Card (JKN-KIS). The government targets that by the end of 2019 health insurance for all Indonesian people will be protected by BPJS Health. However, in reality the Social Security Fund (DJS) available at BPJS Kesehatan continues to run a deficit (Balogh et al., 2011).

Until finally this institution was unable to pay all payment claims submitted by several health facilities (faskes), both hospitals, clinics, health centers, doctors and other medical personnel in a timely manner. This resulted in a decrease in services and a shortage of resources from each health facility, both in terms of budget and the obligation to pay several months' arrears in salaries/honorary medical personnel and the procurement of medical equipment (alkes). A further impact of the BPJS Health budget deficit is that several health facilities refuse to serve JKN patients, especially KIS for the poor and underprivileged. Not a few patients who hold critical KIS to death because they are not served. This condition raises suspicions (from observers of policies and performance of government institutions), that there is a deposit (embezzlement) of the budget at the BPJS Health agency. The reasons put forward by BPJS Health included health facilities providing inaccurate data and incomplete accreditation status of health facilities. The above conditions caused turmoil in the general public and policy observers, especially after several health facilities decided to stop working with BPJS Kesehatan (Astuti, 2019). Whereas since operating on January 1, 2014 the number of BPJS Health participants nationally has increased (Beran et al., 2016).

The performance of BPJS Kesehatan is difficult to reach the target because the average number of participants must increase by at least 1.6 million people per month or double the current achievement. This shows that the increase in the number of participants is not proportional to the performance and availability of adequate resources. Moreover, at the end of 2020 (as of November 1) there was a decrease in the number of participants (temporary deletion) due to the re-registration policy of some JKN participants receiving State Wages. Various problems related to the implementation of BPJS Health as stated above, always come from a limited budget and for Garut Regency itself BPJS Health still has arrears of Rp. 50 billion.

Although some people had lost the trust of some because they had overdue claims of Rp. 3.7 trillion from all health facilities, as of July 1, 2020, all these claims had been paid in full thanks to the entry of the PBI APBN participant contributions of Rp. 4.05 trillion.

Nationally, all JKN program participants through BPJS Health from various categories must be served by various health facilities that have collaborated with BPJS Health or are accredited, both hospitals, health centres, clinics, doctors, pharmacies, opticians, and other health facilities as many as 27,076 units (BPJS -Health, 2020c). Especially in Garut Regency, the number of JKN-KIS program participants continued to increase from 1,587,640 people (72.1%) as of October 2017. Then it increased a year later to 1,740,759 people (78.35%). Then it increased to almost 1.9 million people (85%) in August 2019, then 92% in November 2020, and in January 2021 it decreased to 1,748,218 (72.84%) then rose again to 2,153,772 or 85.65% of the total population of around 2,514,515 people as of August 2021 (Cordery, 2004).

Jamkesda integration participants with PBI status from the Garut Regional Government on August 4, 2021 were 141,331 people. Meanwhile, the number of people who do not have JKN-KIS is 300 thousand people or 14.35% of the total population. Meanwhile, the collectability of JKN contributions from the PBPU segment is still low, only 27.90% or Rp. 39,000,286,000 of the total bill of Rp. 127,167,901,714. This means that as many as 132,712 participants are in arrears with contributions with total arrears of Rp. 88,167,615,714 out of 163,885 PBPU participants. As for the participation of registered business entities as of July 2021, there are only 17 out of 682 units with 27,676 families or 60,643 participants.

Problems related to the implementation of the JKN Program policy through BPJS Health in Indonesia, including in West Java Province and Garut Regency, are an illustration of health service governance in general by the government in a number of countries in the Asia-Pacific region. The image of BPJS in reality does not match reality. There are various problems that are difficult to overcome, one of which is the problem in BPJS claims management. Although there have been efforts from the government in realizing efforts to solve existing problems, these efforts have not been effective due to several inhibiting factors, so it is necessary to establish and apply the integrated IMP (Identity Monitoring Program) concept between Disduk Capil and BPJS (Doz, 2017).

The administrative system is considered complex to be easily understood by the public. It is necessary to socialize to the public about BPJS membership and strengthen coordination with BPJS if there are problems with BPJS patient membership members. In addition, internally in each FKTP also need to improve services, because human resources, especially the administrative division, in addition to computers that have frequent errors, are also still many who have not mastered the use of computers, so they are often wrong in identifying JKN patient participation. The main problem is that the available budget to overcome the weaknesses of resources is still limited, so that the integration of access to health services is still constrained.

Aspects of the dynamics of collaboration are not going well, namely conditions that do not benefit all parties, so that it seems that there is still throwing and waiving of responsibilities (sectoral ego). This is in line with the results of the analysis of BPJS Health problems and their solutions which are found at three levels, namely the policy level, organizational level,

and operational level. Therefore, the problems faced in implementing BPJS urgently require collaborative governance solutions between the Central Government, BPJS, Regional Governments (provincial and district/city) and the community using a systems thinking approach (Wohlgezogen & Zhelyazkov, 2012).

The problem in implementing centralized policies, including the JKN Program by BPJS Health, is that the government faces problems with complex health policy authority at the central level and decentralized authority to the provincial, district and city levels after the birth of Law no. 9 of 2015 concerning Regional Government. This causes the implementation of health services is not optimal. Therefore, to achieve the successful implementation of JKN nationally, a stronger hierarchical relationship structure mechanism is needed at the central level, a stronger BPJS Health bargaining power in the regions, and a stronger policy emphasis from the local government (Gusnita, 2017).

Meanwhile, when viewed from the concept or model of dynamic centralization of the JKN-KIS Program and Jamkesda through BPJS Health nationally, the above problems are caused by a shift in policy authority, gaps in conditions between regions, and conditions on the ground that are often different from national data and assumptions. Therefore, the results of Supriyantoro's research (2014) recommend that this program should apply a model that focuses on the following aspects, has a clear, strong, sustainable action plan, has the same commitment and is forward-looking.

In connection with several problems of implementing governance in the service of the JKN Program through BPJS Health, it is necessary to emphasize the importance of the involvement of various parties to achieve the best health services in Indonesia. This is because the problems that arise in BPJS cannot be adequately addressed through coordination and cooperation steps. Based on several problems and research findings, as stated above, it shows that collaborative governance is one alternative that is considered capable of accelerating the implementation of the National Health Insurance Program (JKN) policy through BPJS Health in the context of equitable access to health services for all citizens. In addition, the importance of collaborative governance is also in order to overcome several problems that make the target number of JKN program participants difficult to achieve and other obstacles at various policy levels.

B. METHOD

This study takes the object of: Collaborative Governance in Policy Implementation of the National Health Insurance Program (JKN) through the Social Security Administering Body (BPJS) of Garut Regency Health. In addition, this study also uses qualitative-descriptive methods, namely to describe problems and solutions, steps for policy implementation, the role of each actor, and the success of policy implementation. This refers to the opinion of Moleong (2013), that qualitative research is a research procedure that produces descriptive data in the form of written or spoken words from people and observable behavior.

The techniques and tools for collecting data in this research include direct observation techniques (observation), interview techniques and documentation studies. While the data

analysis that will be used in this study refers to the Miles and Huberman model (in Sugiyono, 2010) which consists of three flow activities, namely the data reduction stage, namely by selecting data that is important and relevant to the research study, creating categories, removing or replacing unused data. The next step in qualitative data analysis is drawing conclusions and verification, qualitative research conclusions may be able to answer the problem formulation formulated from the beginning, but maybe not, because the problems and formulation of qualitative research problems are still temporary and will develop after being in the field. This research includes the analysis of the data from the reduction and presentation. Interpretation is carried out on data that has met the credibility and objectivity of the research in accordance with the formulation of the problem that has been determined (Moleong, 2012).

C. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

a. Implementation of the National Health Insurance Program Policy at the Health Social Security Administering Body in Garut Regency

According to RI Law no. 9 of 2015 concerning the Second Amendment to the Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government, the function of the regional head is to absorb aspirations, increase participation and follow up on public complaints. Therefore, the implementation, management, and administration of regional government is also a function of regional heads in carrying out their duties and authorities on the basis of democratic principles. The administration of government adheres to the principles as stated in Law No. RI. 28 of 1999 concerning the Implementation of a State that is Clean from Collusion, Corruption, and Nepotism, namely legal certainty, orderly administration, public interest, transparency, proportionate, professional, accountable, efficient, and effective (Hanapiah, 2007).

In connection with the above description, the implementation of good governance in public institutions or organizations (central/regional), adheres to the following three principles, transparency, namely efforts to create trust between the government and the community through the provision of easily accessible information facilities, participation, namely conditions that encourage every citizen to exercise their right to express their opinion in the decision-making process, for the benefit of the community, either directly or indirectly, so that the government process runs according to the principles of people's governance and accountability, namely the government is obliged to account for the administration of government periodically through the elected DPR/MPR directly, publicly, freely and confidentially.

The principles of state administration (public organizations) above emphasize the importance of strategic vision, responsibility, professionalism, commitment, and participation of all parties to build for the advancement of local government that is beneficial to all. This is the reference for local governments in determining policies to describe some of the central authorities that are assigned to the regions. Therefore, local governments and their staff must be able to organize local government through good public services, including in the health sector. In relation to the health sector, to realize optimal and excellent services, a foundation

or direction of activities is needed to achieve these goals through various policies, one of which is the JKN-KIS Program policy through BPJS Health (Houldin et al., 2004).

This is done to provide comprehensive, fair, and equitable opportunities for the entire population to obtain adequate, non-discriminatory health services, protection and insurance. So the implementation of the JKN program at BPJS Health in Garut Regency must include four steps, namely communication between BPJS Health parties, relevant government institutions and private parties; provision of health resources needed in the context of the success of the JKN Program at BPJS Health; disposition of leadership attitudes and capabilities of related institutions towards the JKN Program at BPJS Health; as well as a bureaucratic structure that supports the effectiveness of implementing the rules of the JKN Program on BPJS Health.

Communication, coordination and cooperation are very important to be carried out by BPJS Health as the leading sector of the JKN Program with various related parties, government institutions, private sector, stakeholders and the community. So far, the communication that has occurred is going quite well and continues to improve in a better direction. Support from the Garut Regency government and related institutions managed to completely overcome these problems as of July 1, 2020. This shows that communication is one of the factors that determine the successful implementation of a program (Irwandy, 2016).

In addition, the level of availability of health resources including the availability of quality and quantity must be fulfilled in full, while the resources in question include health personnel (Health HR), both medical personnel (doctors), paramedics (nurses/midwives), and administrative staff in each area. Health facilities, including the resources owned by the BPJS Health agency itself. Other resources include the availability of health facilities (FKTP/FKRTL) and non-RS/Puskesmas such as pharmacies, clinics, independent practice, and others. Meanwhile, the supporting resources for health facilities are the availability of medicines and pharmaceuticals, as well as adequate medical equipment and technology. The resource that is no less important is the availability of the health budget, either directly provided by the government or by each health facility. Because the resources that must be owned by an institution is one aspect that determines the success of implementing program policies that are the duties and obligations of the institution.

Leadership plays a role in realizing the success of the JKN Program at BPJS Health. BPJS Health as a leading sector is an institution that initiates national health insurance for the entire community. Through leadership, conditions are created for mutual understanding, mutual support, and mutual strengthening between relevant institutions and stakeholders as well as the community participating in the program. BPJS Kesehatan continues to improve service commitments by simplifying various membership rules, including optimizing the role of Participant Complaint Handling (PPP) officers in every hospital that is easily accessible to patients (participants), increasing functions and expanding Mobile Customer Services (MCS), simplifying service procedures. hem dialysis (HD), expansion of hospitals in providing electronic queuing systems, expansion of hospitals in providing bed displays and bed occupancy ratio (BOR), expansion of hospitals in operating waiting list services, integration of FKTP/FKRTL information systems with information systems BPJS Health, as well as e-

claim services and MCH claims (Mother-Child Health), family planning services, and others (Kretschmer & Vanneste, 2017).

The smoothness of the service system cannot be separated, of course, it must be supported by administrative completeness of the demographic aspects of prospective participants (KTP, KK and other certificates) provided by the relevant agency (Disdukcapil). Therefore, the Garut Regency Government with its authority assigned the Department of Population and Civil Registration (Disdukcapil) to assist the JKN program participation process effectively and efficiently. On the other hand, the number of health workers (HR) to support the JKN program in Garut Regency is far from sufficient, both in terms of quality and quantity. These health workers include doctors, paramedics/nurses, midwives and other formal health workers. Especially when dealing with the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic in the last two years. Even though the number of nurses is increasing every year, the number of nurses still does not meet the ideal ratio to population in improving the health status of the community.

The ideal ratio for the fulfillment of doctors' health workers is 1:2,500. Currently, the number of doctors has reached 160 people and when compared to the current population of around 2.6 million people, the number of doctors should be 1,035 people. Meanwhile, the ratio of 1.158 midwives (PTT and PNS) to the total population is 1:2,236 from the ideal 1:1.135. This problem causes the occurrence of health facilities services that are not optimal for JKN participants and the general public, such as queuing at each examination and treatment poly, including administering visit data for JKN program participants. This has a chain impact on the occurrence of service delays at BPJS Health caused by incomplete file administration carried out by health workers and health facilities (Kurniawan, 2007),

Overall, the procurement of Health Human Resources has actually followed the minimum health standards at the Puskesmas in accordance with the Minister of Health Regulation no. 43 of 2019 concerning Puskesmas Article 17, namely the eligibility for minimum service standards for Puskesmas is the fulfillment of general practitioners, dentists, nurses, midwives, health promotion workers, environmental sanitation workers, nutritionists, pharmacists or pharmaceutical technical personnel and medical laboratory technology experts. In addition, there is also an agreement with the relevant institutions in bringing in the required facilities and infrastructure through the BLU (Public Service Agency) method of Puskesmas.

Based on this problem, the government must provide some facilities for graduates of health and medical schools to immediately apply their knowledge in a number of health facilities. The government should not be half-hearted in recruiting these prospective health workers to become permanent employees through official ties that provide certainty for their future. If necessary, with the fact of integrity and work agreement, if you have graduated from education, you must serve in your area of origin for a certain time. Then it is added to the fact that the availability of the health budget for the JKN Program in Garut Regency is not sufficient, one of which is caused by the receipt of contributions from various sources (types) of participants which is much smaller than the BPJS obligation to pay claims from all health facilities in Garut Regency.

Nevertheless, the problem of arrears or budget deficit of BPJS Kesehatan Garut has been resolved. With the increased awareness of BPJS Kesehatan Garut participants, there has also been an increase in the number and percentage of contributions received from various

segments by BPJS Kesehatan, either through independent contributions or contributions assisted by the APBD. This of course reduces the amount of the deficit or arrears in contributions for participants who have not fulfilled their contribution obligations. Therefore, it must continue to be improved through socialization and training of participants so that there is an increase in awareness of participants, not only relying on government subsidies (APBD) which must also be shared with other government policy posts. As of October 2020, 132,638 PBPU (81.82%) are in arrears from a total of 162,108 participants, while those with current contributions are less than 20%. To overcome the problem of arrears, referring to the existing regulations, support for the provision of the JKN program budget in Garut Regency is very good, including the following, in accordance with Permendagri No. 33 of 2017, the central government helps contributions for the poor and underprivileged (PBI). In Presidential Decree No. 64 of 2020 the nomenclature of PBI becomes PBPU and BP Pemda or PB APBD which for March 2021 the number reached 139,200 people (Achim, 2016).

BPJS Kesehatan continues to improve service commitments by simplifying various membership rules, including optimizing the role of Participant Complaint Handling (PPP) officers in every hospital that is easily accessible to patients (participants), increasing functions and expanding Mobile Customer Services (MCS), simplifying service procedures. hemodialysis (HD), expansion of hospitals in providing electronic queuing systems, expansion of hospitals in providing bed displays and bed occupancy ratio (BOR), expansion of hospitals in operating waiting list services, integration of FKTP/FKRTL information systems with information systems BPJS Health, as well as e-claim services and KIA (Mother-Child Health) claims, family planning services, and others. The smoothness of the service system cannot be separated, of course, it must be supported by administrative completeness of the demographic aspects of prospective participants (KTP, KK and other certificates) provided by the relevant agency (Disdukcapil). Therefore, the Garut Regency Government with its authority assigned the Department of Population and Civil Registration (Disdukcapil) to assist the JKN program participation process effectively and efficiently.

b. Community Health Development Index Level in Garut Regency through Collaborative Governance in the Implementation of the National Health Insurance Program at BPJS Health in Garut Regency

Relationships in collaboration are very complex because the process is constantly evolving, interactive and dynamic. Interdisciplinary collaboration is a process of exchanging knowledge, expertise, action and developing mutually beneficial relationships to generate new ideas through dynamic interactions. The formation of shared values, namely improving public health is the main goal of collaboration in the health sector. The coordination carried out by the local government in this case BPJS Kesehatan Garut Regency has been carried out since the planning stage by involving various elements, both institutions within the local government starting from upper level to lower level (RT/RW), companies (private sector), JKN cadres, health observers, to the general public. Coordination is the integration and alignment of the goals, plans, and activities that have been set for all elements spread across various work units or functional units to achieve common goals or to produce uniform,

harmonious, efficient and effective actions. Coordination is a step that must be taken by the leadership to ensure that all work activities run harmoniously and efficiently (Widya, 2017).

One form of good coordination is the establishment of cooperation in an effort to cover all BPJS Kesehatan Garut arrears against a number of health facilities, so that currently there are no more incidents of health facilities refusing to serve BPJS patients. In addition, through good coordination, the fulfillment of the need for medicines and medical devices is also not fairly smooth and does not burden the community too much or increase the length of treatment time for patients participating in the JKN Program. With any type of treatment and any disease, participants do not need to worry about the costs that will be incurred, because everything has been guaranteed by BPJS Kesehatan for all classes.

The support of companies (private sector) for the JKN program is also increasing, this is due to the increasing awareness of the importance of health at affordable costs. The company does not only provide its own health facilities internally, but also requires its employees to become participants in the JKN program facilitated by the company. This increase in participants did not just appear, but was caused by the awareness of employees about their health so far thanks to the guidance, both from internal companies and from outside (health facilities officers or BPJS Health officers). The increase in participants from the private sector was also driven by the Presidential Instruction No. 8 of 2017 concerning Optimizing the Implementation of the JKN Program which implies certain sanctions for companies that do not register or require their employees to become participants of the JKN Program (Eka & Pardi, 2019).

Private sector support also shows that company managers are very concerned about the health of their employees, so that productivity is maintained. However, private support is still not optimal considering that there are still companies that have not provided their company profiles, especially those related to health services for their employees. Even from early January 2020 - March 2021, there was a decrease in the number of JKN program participation through BPJS Kesehatan Garut from 65,333 people to 57,880 people from around 830 active business entities. However, coordination must be further improved in order to increase private support. In addition, the participation of citizens to become members (participation) of the JKN program through BPJS in Garut Regency is arguably very enthusiastic.

This is a form of coordination between all stakeholders. However, in terms of quality, especially the commitment and responsibility of participation, it still has to be improved, so it is the duty of all parties to improve it, as well as to improve the quality of other services, so that if the target of all citizens to become participants in the JKN program is achieved by the end of this year, then it is only up to the government how to do it. regions that accommodate all participants' health service needs can be well served through the provision of human resources that meet expectations in quantity and quality, the provision of qualified medical equipment, as well as improving the quality of health services for all citizens without discrimination.

Until the end of 2020 the participation of the JKN Program through BPJS Health in Garut reached 92% (2.2 million out of a population of 2.4 million). This means that the enthusiasm of the citizens to participate in participating in the JKN Program through BPJS Health is very good. It's just a matter of coaching and coordination that must be further improved by all stakeholders to increase mutual commitment. Participants' commitment continues to increase, although it is not optimal. This includes service procedures that follow the rules, compliance with the rules, and payment of membership fees. Therefore, to balance this commitment, the BPJS Kesehatan service center publishes the JKN Faskes Mobile Application which includes four primary service functions including first contact care, continuity, coordinate of care, and comprehensive care, as well as Pandawa (Administrative Services via WA) (Nasution, 2019).

As for the form of consensus of all stakeholders, the implementation of the JKN program in Garut Regency is going very well. The latest data on August 31, 2021 shows that there is extraordinary support from the Manpower Office for the participant segment from companies. This increases the level of collectability of companies in Garut Regency, although there are still 8% arrears from 70-80 companies. This shows the company's full support for the JKN Program for employees. The positive aspect that can be taken is that the company is helped by the existence of health insurance for its employees, not only guarantees when they are sick or in need of treatment, but the company also needs assurance that its employees are in good physical and mental health while working to increase company productivity. For this reason, every company should not have the term arrears in contributions for its employees who are participants in the JKN Program through BPJS Health. All you have to do is think about and find a solution, what if there is a problem, how to convey it objectively to BPJS Health to find a way out.

The ability of the drivers in implementing the National Health Insurance Program through BPJS Health in Garut Regency includes leadership skills, the ability of related institutions to identify problems that occur and map out infrastructure conditions and the health status of residents, as well as the ability of natural drivers of socialization and program development. The ability of the drivers is an important component in the implementation of the policy of the JKN Program through BPJS Health. In relation to the leadership of the BPJS Kesehatan Garut Regency in implementing the JKN Program, communication is a very important aspect in maintaining mutual understanding and exchanging information with interested parties, especially health facilities managers. Until now, communication is still quite well maintained and continues to be intensified, especially after the problem of very large arrears about a year ago. In the end, with communication, there is mutual understanding to help reduce the burden of the budget arrears experienced, so that BPJS Kesehatan Garut Regency can be said to have been able to cover all arrears to each health facility (Nurhasana, 2018).

The aspect of coordination from below is also very important to help community members who will get BPJS membership through data collection carried out by village/kelurahan officials, regarding the conditions for obtaining the appropriate type of BPJS membership. Meanwhile for companies (wage providers), coordination is also important to convince employees who have the right to receive health care benefits through registration of employee

participation on behalf of the company. This communication is also carried out as socialization every time there is a new policy regulation from BPJS Health, such as adjustments to the amount of contributions, as well as the rights and obligations of each participant, including services that can be covered by BPJS Health.

Related to leadership coordination and communication, consistency in providing budget assistance must also be maintained with a high commitment to optimizing the coverage of JKN program participation. Another thing related to leadership is the firmness of the leadership in enforcing rules and sanctions. This is in accordance with Presidential Instruction Number 8 of 2017 concerning Optimizing the Implementation of the JKN Program, including the following, allocating a budget within the framework of the JKN Program, ensuring that all residents are registered in the JKN Program, providing health service facilities and infrastructure according to health standards and qualified health human resources in Indonesia. Their respective regions, and ensure BUMD to register and provide complete and correct data for administrators and workers and their family members and the JKN Program (Pertiwi & Nurcahyanto, 2016).

The ability of the drivers to identify problems in the implementation of the JKN Program through BPJS Health is an important aspect to achieve program efficiency and effectiveness. The capabilities possessed by the drivers of the JKN program policies in Garut Regency are quite good or quite successful. The results of the problem identification from the drivers are coordinated between the participants and the designated health facilities according to their domicile or directly to the local BPJS health office. The ability to identify community health service problems and mapping health service problems must continue to be improved, not only emphasizing on the drivers, but also on aspects that are able to encourage these movers to have a high commitment to work, such as guaranteeing the welfare and future of the community members. The driver also needs to be considered. For example, his employee status must have certainty that can support his dedication in ensuring the health of all citizens.

This means that, in addition to building awareness among the people and program participants, the movers must also pay attention to the need for self-actualization. This is in line with the findings, that the efforts made by the government to overcome the problem of BPJS Health claims are not running effectively due to several factors, including internal factors regarding the disbursement of BPJS claims and external factors, namely people are less aware of how to manage BPJS cards accompanied by the perception that BPJS card management is troublesome as well as several other factors related to curative efforts (Qalbi et al., 2020).

The final indicator of the implementation of the JKN Program through BPJS Health in Garut Regency is the success of increasing the IPKM, which is based on an increase in Life Expectancy (AHH); a decrease in the maternal mortality rate from 100,000 live births (AKI), the infant mortality rate from 1000 births (IMR), and the prevalence rate of children under five with malnutrition and disease. The series of indicators in the IPKM above are in accordance with the model of the public health approach developed by WHO. The basis of the IPKM conceptual framework is the monitoring and evaluation of the health system. WHO

uses the “The six building blocks of health system” approach to describe the six pillars of strengthening the health system? The six pillars of the health system consist of 1) health services, 2) health workers, 3) health information systems, 4) access to medical devices/vaccines/technology, 5) health financing, and 6) leadership and health resources (Ministry of Health, 2019).

The general principles of indicators used in the preparation of the IPKM are simple, easy, measurable, useful, reliable, and timely. The selected indicators in the IPKM show more of the impact of the previous year's health development and become a reference for planning health development programs for the following year. IPKM has been developed since 2010 to monitor health development at the provincial and district/city levels. Health development indicators measured in the IPKM include toddler health, maternal health, infectious diseases, non-communicable diseases, reproductive health, and nutritional status (Suprianto & Mutiarin, 2017).

Acceleration of development on the health dimension in Garut Regency really needs to continue to be carried out on the determinant factors that affect these dimensions, which are not limited to the health sector, but involve almost all development sectors which include the construction of health facilities and infrastructure, infrastructure, sanitation, education and others. Etc. basically, efforts that must be made must be directed at increasing the adequacy and accessibility of the population to health facilities and increasing the responsiveness of the population to these health facilities. The acceleration of the implementation of health programs to reduce infant mortality and maternal mortality, along with efforts to create adequate health facilities and more equitable medical personnel, must absolutely be maintained and improved in consistency. So that it is expected to guarantee public access to health services optimally. In addition, it is hoped that the acceleration of HDI achievement will not only rely on technical services, but must be integrated with the tasks of the sub-district, sub-district and village government, and be more directed to improving the infrastructure of the Puskesmas and its entire network.

D. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion, it can be concluded several things related to collaborative governance steps in the implementation of the National Health Insurance Program (JKN) through the Health Social Security Administration (BPJS) in Garut Regency, namely as follows, Implementation of the JKN Program policy on BPJS Health in Garut Regency has been going pretty well. Although it cannot be separated from several shortcomings, aspects of the successful implementation of the policy are running properly in accordance with the applicable laws and regulations. The steps for implementing this program policy are carried out through communication, coordination and collaboration between BPJS Health as the leading sector and related government institutions, private parties, stakeholders and also the community or program participants. Another step is through the provision of adequate health resources in quality and quantity, as well as a leadership disposition to influence staff and subordinate institutions to support each other's success in the program. The final step is to simplify the bureaucratic structure of the administration of

services for participants or prospective program participants in order to obtain health services effectively and efficiently.

REFERENCES

1. Ansell, C., dan Gash, A. (2007). Collaborative governance in theory and practice. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 18, 543-571. Published by Oxford University Press.
2. Balogh, S., Emerson K, & Nabatchi T, (2011). An Integrative Framework for Collaborative Governance. *Journal of public administration research and theory*, 22(1). 1–29.
3. Beran, D., Perone, S.A., Alcoba, G., Bischoff, Al, Bussien, C.L., Eperon, G., Hagon, O., Heller, O., Bausch, F.J., Perone, N., Vogel, T. & Chappuis, F. (2016). Partnerships in global health and collaborative governance: lessons learnt from the Division of Tropical and Humanitarian Medicine at the Geneva University Hospitals. *Journal of Globalization and Health of BioMed Central*. 12:14. 1-13. DOI 10.1186/s12992-016-0156-x.
4. Cordery, J. (2004). Another case of the Emperor's new clothes? *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*.
5. Doz, Y. (2017). "Inter-partner learning in strategic alliances". In *Collaborative Strategy: Critical Issues for Alliances and Networks*. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar Publishing.
6. Gulati, R., Wohlgezogen, F., & Zhelyazkov, P. (2012). The two facets of collaboration: Cooperation and coordination in strategic alliances. *The Academy of Management Annals*, 6(1), 531-583.
7. Gusnita, Ari. (2017). Analisis Implementasi Jaminan Sosial Nasional pada BPJS Kota Metro. *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Penelitian dan PKM Sosial, Ekonomi dan Humaniora Universitas Islam Bandung*, Vol 7, No.3, Th. 2017. 692-698
8. Hanapiah, P. (2007). Good Governance: Membangun Masyarakat Yang Demokratis dan Nasionalis. *Artikel Ilmiah FISIP UNPAD*.
9. Houldin, A. D., Naylor, M. D., & Haller, D. G. (2004). Physician-nurse collaboration in research in the 21st century. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 22(5), 774-776.
10. Irwandy. (2016). Evaluasi pelaksanaan program jkn di indonesia: kajian literatur. *Jurnal Kebijakan Kesehatan Indonesia*. Vol. 05 No. 03. September 2016. 110-114
11. Kretschmer, T., & Vanneste, B. (2017). "Collaboration in strategic alliances: cooperation and coordination". In *Collaborative Strategy: Critical Issues for Alliances and Networks*. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar Publishing.
12. Kurniawan, T. 2007. Pergeseran Paradigma Administrasi Publik: Dari Perilaku Model Klasik dan NPM ke Good Governance. *Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi Negara*, Vol. 7.
13. Lang, Achim. (2016). Collaborative Governance in Health and Technology Policy: The Use and Effects of Procedural Policy Instruments. *Journal of Institute of Public Management, Zurich University of Applied Sciences, Bahnhofplatz 12, 8401 Winterthur, Switzerland*. DOI: 10.1177/0095399716664163. Published on August 10, 2016 by Sage Administration & Society p.1–27. Available: aas.sagepub.com
14. Leksmanawati, Widya. (2017). *Tata Kelola Kolaboratif Kebijakan Jaminan Kesehatan Nasional*. Disertasi Program Doktor Ilmu Sosial dan Ilmu Politik Universitas Indonesia, Jakarta
15. Maryuni, S., Eka, A. & Pardi. (2019). Sosialisasi program jkn dalam meningkatkan partisipasi kepesertaan mandiri bpjs kesehatan di desa sungai belidak kecamatan sungai kakap kabupaten kubu raya. *Jurnal Spirit Publik Volume 14, Nomor 1, April 2019*. 1-15
16. Moleong, L.J. (2012). *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*. Bandung: Penerbit PT Remaja Rosdakarya
17. Nasution, C.R. (2019). *Pola Hubungan Pusat-Daerah dalam Implementasi Program JKN*. Disertasi Program Doktor Fakultas Kedokteran, Kesehatan Masyarakat, dan Keperawatan, Universitas Gadjah Mada, Yogyakarta
18. Nurhasana, R. (2018). *Kesinambungan Pembayaran Iuran JKN PBPU di Jabodetabek*. Disertasi. Program Studi Ilmu Kesehatan Masyarakat, Fakultas Ilmu Kesehatan Masyarakat, Universitas Indonesia. (tidak diterbitkan).
19. Pertiwi, M. dan Nurcahyanto, H. (2016). Efektivitas program bpjs kesehatan di kota semarang. (Studi Kasus pada Pasien Pengguna Jasa BPJS Kesehatan di Puskesmas Srandol). *Departemen Administrasi Publik*

- Fakultas Ilmu Sosial dan Ilmu Politik Universitas Diponegoro. 1-14
20. Qalbi, N.S., Sanna, A.A.T. & Mustafa, A.A. (2020). Implementasi imp (identity monitoring program): upaya penyelesaian manajemen klaim dalam jaminan kesehatan. *Jurnal Legislatif Fakultas Hukum UNHAS*. Volume 3 (2), Juni 2020. 219-234
 21. Suprianto, A. & Mutiarin, D. (2017). Evaluasi pelaksanaan jkn (studi tentang hubungan stakeholder, model pembiayaan dan outcome jkn di kabupaten bantul provinsi diy. *Journal of Governance And Public Policy*. Vol. 4 No. 1 February 2017. 71-107.